

EXPLORING ENGLISH-URDU CODE-SWITCHING IN DIGITAL ADVERTISING: A CASE STUDY OF KFC PAKISTAN

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Abstract

This paper explores code-switching in Urdu and English languages used in Facebook post captions of KFC Pakistan during the period of September to December 2025. Based on a mixed-method approach, 95 captions were examined keeping in view frequency, functions and implications of code-switching. Results indicate that the frequency of code-switching was 19 in 14 captions, with the majority of these instances being intra-sentential and with the purpose of persuasion, cultural appropriateness, and interest to the audience. The paper emphasizes the role of bilingual language practices in brand identity and the indicators of approaching the Pakistani audiences through the social media marketing.

INTRODUCTION

In a world that is growing more globalized in media terms, the language used in advertising and in corporate communication is becoming a strategic tool that defines the way in which brands relate to their consumers. Marketers in multilingual societies like Pakistan where English and Urdu are both functional languages have the tendency of mixing the linguistic systems to produce messages that are both culturally and emotionally appealing to the consumers. An example of such practice is code switching: the alternating of two or more languages in a communicative situation, that has received extensive sociolinguistic and media discourse research (Poplack, 1980; Gumperz, 1982). Code switching is an expression of multifaceted processes of social, cultural and identity, and its use in marketing texts can show how brands are able to mediate between global identities and local cultural sensibility.

Facebook, as well as other social media sites, have become significant platforms of brand communication and interaction. Social media unlike the conventional media enables brands to directly address their audiences in a more

conversational manner and this is usually a mixture of information and cultural indications as well as engaging aspects. A study of the digital communication emphasizes that the process of language mixing on social media is not exclusive to user generated content; institutional and branded use of bilingual practices to create audience engagement and strengthen brand personality also exists (Hajra and Akram, 2025; Jamali, Rasool, and Batool, 2022). Nevertheless, although the literature on code switching in user communication and conventional advertisements is extensive, little research has been conducted on the use of the code switching in branded social media posts by corporate entities in Pakistan. This is one of the gaps in the comprehension of the manner in which the language bilingual practices are capitalized in the corporate online discourse. KFC Pakistan is one of the branches of the international fast food chain that engages actively on Facebook to market its products and campaigns as well as events. As the linguistic diversity of Pakistan and the use of digital media are unique, it is notable that KFC Pakistan needs to explore how it has employed language,

especially English and Urdu in its Facebook captions to inform its audience. The initial analysis reveals that part of the captions incorporate Urdu words into the predominantly English text, which could indicate that the code switching is done intentionally to make the text culturally relevant, emotionally appealing, and engaging. However, the prevalence and role of this practice have not been subjectively analyzed in the theoretical framework, which links sociolinguistic theory with the discourse of marketing.

This paper is placed at the intersection of sociolinguistics and media discourse analysis relying on the theory of code switching by Poplack (1980) and Gumperz (1982). It also includes functional views on the use of more than one language (Myers Scotton, 1993; Auer, 1998) and semiotic views on meaning making in media texts (Hall, 1997; Barthes, 1977). To answer three major questions, the study focuses on the Facebook captions posted by KFC Pakistan between September and December 2025: how often code switching is applied, what purposes does it serve, and how it supports the positioning and the audience engagement strategy of the brand. The insights into these dynamics will add to the further debates on how global brands adjust their communication strategies to the local context in multilingual societies. It will also give information on how the linguistic decisions of digital branding are indicative of socio cultural practices of negotiation and consumer interaction in Pakistani digital spaces.

Research Questions

1. How frequently is code-switching used in KFC Pakistan's Facebook posts?
2. What functions does code-switching serve in these posts?
3. How does code-switching reflect KFC Pakistan's brand positioning and engagement with its audience?

Literature Review

Advertising and digital media has become a more and more popular location of studying the patterns of bilingual communication, especially in multilingual societies like Pakistan. An increasing amount of literature has been examining the concept of code switching, the additional application of more than a single language in a communicative situation, as an act of strategy in

media and marketing communications. This section is a review of studies that place in context and support the current research on code switching in Facebook captions of KFC Pakistan and is situated within the wider context of code switching in advertising and digital media.

Code switching is not the spontaneous linguistic alternation, but it is a strategy of communication that can make messages more appealing, culturally relevant and interesting to the audiences in media discourse (Iqbal, 2011). Code switching can also be used in advertising in the form of a slogan or a message that persuades to attract the attention of bilingual audiences (Khan et al., 2025). As an illustration, Khan, Tahmeed, and Nawab (2025) examined TV advertisements in Pakistan and found that code switching is effectively employed to highlight the product attributes and attract both Urdu and English consumers so that an advertisement can appeal to different consumer groups. The presence and intent of code switching in the display marketing texts are also evident in studies that concentrate on billboards and other outdoor advertisements in Pakistan. Habib, Khokhar, and Mustafa (2025) discovered that almost fifty percent of the analyzed billboard ads had code switching with a common use of English in the Urdu language as the way of making slogans more interesting and attractive. This suggests that language practices of bilingualism are used to gain attention and cultural hybridity in the consumer environments. Previous studies on television advertisements in Pakistan by Riaz (2019) also support the fact that English has a strong impact on Urdu in the content of advertisement, and the use of English words is seen to permeate the language of the local media as a whole as a sociocultural trend. This long term effect substantiates the idea that advertisers use bilingual resources to match the messages to the current, cosmopolitan identities in the Pakistani markets. Although most of the advertising literature has been concentrated on conventional media, new studies have resorted to digital platforms whereby language practices are quickly changing with the dynamics of the audience. The situation in social media, specifically, demonstrates the dynamic tendency of language alternation, which is associated with identity performance and cultural negotiation (Hajra and Akram, 2025). Based on data on Instagram and Tik Tok, Hajra and Akram (2025) found that code switching was a significant

tool used by Pakistani youth to show their identity, feelings, and cultural creativity on the internet. This is in line with the current research subject of Facebook captions which are used within the same interactive digital environment. Even though most of the current studies on social media are based on user generated content, and not on brand communication, results of Twitter contexts have shown that bilingual users often blend languages within the same tweet, which means that bilingualism in the context of mediated communication is a common phenomenon (Jamali, Rasool, and Batool, 2022). Similarly, Shah, Irfan, and Akram (2025) in their study found that English-Urdu code-mixing in social media advertisements functions as a tool to negotiate cultural identity. This makes it clear that branded content like the captions used by KFC Pakistan is another channel that sociolinguistic practices can be practiced in a particular way that has functional significance. In these settings, researchers have noted that code switching has significant functional and socio cultural purposes. In advertising, it may be used as a convincing tool, with the linguistic repertoires of consumers used to impact and increase the appeal (Khan et al., 2025). Bilingual forms have the ability to bear cultural indicators that denote modernity, cosmopolitanism, or local identity - putting the brands in the sociolects people desire on social media and elsewhere. Also, the use of English language in the local language such as Urdu is a sign of language development and bargaining in the media discourse where language bilingualism options represent the larger patterns of media consumption and identity. The studies of language variation in advertising and online media emphasize that code switching turns into a sort of cultural expression and a way of connecting the global forces with the local tastes (Riaz, 2019). Although earlier research has conducted a strong study that has been compiled and published on the concept of code switching in classic advertisements and user generated digital content, there is a significant gap in the literature that explores the concept of brand generated social media captions in the Pakistani context. Majority of the literature on digital bilingualism focuses on the user practices instead of institutional marketing language and hence there is a gap in studies that systematically examines how brands strategically exploit bilingual

resources in social media texts to create identity and to engage audiences.

The gap identified in the present study is that it deals with a single corporate social media situation, Facebook captions of KFC Pakistan and evaluates the frequency and roles of the Urdu English code switching behavior during a specific period of time. This expands upon previous work in the field of bilingual advertisement by placing the concept of code switching within the context of brand communication in e-marketing.

Methodology

The proposed study is based on a mixed-method approach, whose main emphasis is on qualitative analysis and quantitative descriptive part. The qualitative dimension addresses the linguistic patterns, functions, and situations of code-switching in Facebook captions in KFC Pakistan, whereas the quantitative one offers the number of occurrences of code-switching in order to demonstrate the frequency of using Urdu words in the English captions.

The data sets include 95 Facebook post captions of KFC Pakistan and they were gathered chronologically between September and December 2025. The captures of the posts were taken into account only; comments, replies or hashtags were not taken into account to keep the consistency. The first and second captions between 1st September, 2025 and 31st December, 2025 were considered to form a complete and representative sample of Facebook marketing discourse of the brand. All captions were examined to establish the occurrence of a code-switching.

To follow the aim of this research, code-switching can be defined as the use of words or phrases of Urdu in English captions or vice versa. Such brand or campaign names like KFC, Mithao Bhook were not counted as code-switching. Hashtags were also excluded from the study. The captions were gathered through a manual process, that is, on the official Facebook page of KFC Pakistan in chronological order, beginning with the latest one on 31st December 2025 and moving back to 1st September 2025. All the captions were noted word to word to maintain the linguistic subtlety. There were 95 captions that were put together to be analyzed.

The steps used in the analysis were three:

Frequency Analysis: The presence or absence of code-switching in each caption was checked. The

count of captions that had code-switching was summed up.

Functional Analysis: Code-switching captions were examined in terms of the functional roles of the code-switching, e.g. persuasion, humor, cultural relevance, and appeal to the audience.

Brand Positioning Analysis: The research paper has analyzed how code-switching English-Urdu is used in KFC Pakistan as the brand positioning and approach to local population.

Theoretical Framework

The theory of code-switching proposed by Poplack (1980) and Gumperz (1982) forms the basis of the research. Also the functional approach (Myers-Scotton, 1993; Auer, 1998) is also used to comprehend the reasons of code-switching in marketing communication and its aim to persuade, to be culturally relevant and to engage the audience in marketing communication. Finally the analysis of captions as signifying texts is analyzed by insights of semiotics and sociolinguistics (Hall, 1997; Barthes, 1977) which shows how the language choice plays a role in the creation of the brand

identity and making meaning in the Facebook posts of KFC Pakistan.

Data Analysis

Frequency Analysis

The first step in the analysis was the frequency of the use of the code-switching of the captions of Facebook posts of KFC Pakistan in the months of September to December of 2025. A total of 95 captions were gathered in a sequence to have a thorough representation of the social media conversation of the brand. The caption was scrutinized thoroughly to decide whether there was Urdu-English code-switching, which entails the use of Urdu words or phrases in captions that were in English. The count did not include brand names (e.g., "KFC") or official campaign titles because it was necessary to preserve analytical consistency and consider only the linguistic alternation. Out of the 95 captions, 14 captions were found to contain instances of code-switching, which constitutes approximately 14.73...% of the total dataset. This indicates that while KFC Pakistan predominantly uses English in its social media captions, code-switching is selectively employed in a smaller subset of posts.

Table 1
Frequency and Percentage of Captions with Code-Switching

Total Captions	Captions with Code-Switching	Percentage
95	14	14.73..%

It was found that the code-switching followed a regular linguistic pattern, and it was intra-sentential, that is, the Urdu words are placed in the middle of an English sentence. The dataset did not contain any cases of inter-sentential or tag switching. More often, Urdu words like *Yaari*, *Bhook* or culturally reminiscent phrases were incorporated in English captions, perhaps, to create familiarity to the culture and have an emotional appeal to the audience. The fact that 14 out of the captions contain code-switching implies that the brand used it strategically and not as a form of language mixing. This is consistent with the evidence of bilingual advertisement research,

which indicates that selective code-switching could be used to emphasize culturally important ideas, generate interest, and dissimilar messages within a competitive marketing ecosystem (Khan et al., 2025; Habib et al., 2025). The comparatively low frequency also means that social media strategy by KFC Pakistan is more of the English-dominant one which can be oriented to convey the image of the modern, cosmopolitan brand. Nevertheless, the inclusion of Urdu words in the few posts can be seen as an attempt by the brand to stay culturally relevant, and appeal to local readers, especially when focusing on emotional, relationship, or culturally-specific concepts, like friendship or experiences.

Figure1 Percentage of Captions with Code-Switching

This visual representation provides a clear overview of the extent to which code-switching is used in KFC Pakistan's Facebook marketing discourse.

Functions of Code-Switching

The discussion of the 14 captions that include code switching indicates that strategic mixing of Urdu and English has several communicative and marketing purposes. It is, in part, one of the main functions to establish emotional and relational resonance with the audience. Captions like "A *real yaar* can read your mind without even having to tell..." and "here's celebrating *tumhari* forever wali..." The Urdu words such as "yaar" and sentences such as "tumhari humari forever wali" are used in English sentences to create a sense of friendship, trust and nostalgia. The local expressions in Urdu language allow KFC to appeal to its local customers at a personal level and one that is culturally significant, to form a perception of the brand as friendly, nurturing and socially conscious.

Persuasion and engagement of the audience is another important role that is seen. Captions like "Your KFC *Yaari* moments deserve the spotlight! DM us your KFC *Yaari* moments..." and "*Yaari* loading..." promote involvement, asking the users to share experiences, participate in competitions, or look forward to the release of new products. The integration of Urdu word or culturally sensitive phrases in the English captions is an added advantage because it makes the message more relatable and catchy. These interactive and playful

features of these bilingual elements are indicative of the brand attempting to use a friendly, informal, and participatory voice in social media.

Moreover, there is code-switching in order to incorporate global brand identity and local cultural relevance. Most captions keep up with the English language as the main language of conveying product details, prices, or promotions, and Urdu words are also sprinkled in strategic places to add a touch of culture, humor, or stress. As an example, the captions that advertise the Strips, "*Chips N' Dips* Box, like: *Haddi out, fun in!*" or "*Na game mein haddi, na bite mein,*" mix English and Urdu to form catchy, memorable phrases and phrases which will be able to appeal to the local audience and at the same time keep the international representation of KFC as a modern, stylish brand. The practice enables the brand to negotiate between the globalized discourse of marketing and the local consumer culture, as it shows sensitivity to the culture and creativity in language.

Furthermore, the information indicates that code-switching can have a useful and descriptive purpose, especially in the process of emphasizing product features or benefits in an entertaining manner. Phrases like "*No more haddi! Get the brand new Strips, Chips N Dips Box at only Rs. 1190!*" fuse English and Urdu to convey the main selling point of the product and at the same time produce a catchy and convincing message. This show that code-switching is not only a stylistic device but a good tactic to emphasize certain product features

in a contextualized manner in a culturally sensitive manner.

Overall, the functional analysis shows that the application of code-switching in Facebook captions by KFC Pakistan is intentional and complex. The mixing of the language between Urdu and English helps to create emotional appeal, brand recognition, persuasion, and cultural localization of the marketing messages thus forming an active and interactive communication strategy that will appeal to the bilingual consumers.

Positioning of the Brand and Engagement with Audience

The review of KFC Pakistan Facebook captions shows that the strategic application of the code-switching between Urdu and English is at the heart of creating the brand identity and positioning the brand as a global and at the same time, local brand. The use of captions like *"Your KFC Yaari moments deserve the spotlight! make this possible. DM us your KFC Yaari moments..."* and *"Yaari loading..."* the brand sets itself as interactive, youthful and community based. The repetition of the word *Yaari* is used as a cultural indicator and associates KFC with the values of friendship, loyalty, and common experiences, which the Pakistani audiences can strongly relate to. Introducing local linguistic and cultural allusions into the English captions, KFC reaffirms the feeling of familiarity and belonging, prompting users to view the brand not as a food supplier, but as a member of their social and cultural lives.

Moreover, the captions reveal the conscious attempt of KFC to reconcile the international brand norms and local consumer interactions. The product information, pricing, and promotional information are in English as it has a global identity, KFC. In the meantime, Urdu words and expressions that are culturally known, like, *"tumhari humari forever wali, Haddi out, fun in"*, *"Na game mein haddi, na bite mein"* are tactfully used to generate humor, stress and emotional feelings. This bi-lingual approach places KFC as a cosmopolitan but culturally aware brand, one that can attract both modern and urban consumers and those who are sensitive to local linguistic and cultural authenticity.

The code-switching of the captions is also a device of audience involvement and participatory marketing. Captions that encourage the followers

to post their experiences or wait for the launch of a product such as *"Your KFC Yaari moments deserve the spotlight! DM us your KFC Yaari moments..."* encourage the interaction and community-building. KFC decreases the gap between the brand and the consumers by talking to the audience in a mixed linguistic manner that resembles real life conversations, making the tone conversational and friendly, which promotes the involvement of the users and brand loyalty. Moreover, there were also humorous phrases such as *Haddi out, fun in!* simplify product messaging and at the same time create hype on social media.

In general, the strategic localization of the brand positioning is reflected in the functional implementation of the code-switching. The fact of language bilingualism is used by the KFC Pakistan to emphasize the cultural relevance, to build consumer connections, and to portray itself as the brand that perceives and is engaged in the social and emotional environment of its users. Using a mix of English to be clear and universal and Urdu to be cultural and humorous, KFC establishes an interactive, dynamic, and culturally sensitive digital presence and supports the brand identity and interest of the audience on Facebook.

Conclusion

This study has proven the importance of researching code switching of Facebook captions of KFC Pakistan by placing the research at the border of sociolinguistics, media discourse, and digital marketing. By pointing out the commonness of bilingual language use in multilingual cultures such as Pakistan, it points out how brands are using alternate use of Urdu and English as a way of boosting cultural relevance, audience interest and brand value. The literature review reveals that code switching has been a subject of extensive research in mainstream media and user generated digital content, but there is a knowledge gap on its application in corporate social media communication. The research questions and objectives used in this research will help fill this gap by systematizing the frequency, functions, and brand positioning that is expressed in the form of code-switching in the Facebook captions at KFC Pakistan.

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